

EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES OF UNIDIRECTIONAL FLAX/EPOXY COMPOSITES WITH TWISTED YARNS

Ilya Straumit*, Farida Bensadoun, Stepan V. Lomov, Martine Wevers

Department of Materials Engineering, KU Leuven, Belgium

*Email: straumit.ilya@mtm.kuleuven.be

Keywords: Flax/epoxy composite, Properties, Twist, X-ray tomography

ABSTRACT

The paper presents results of the modelling of unidirectional flax/epoxy composite samples to predict their effective properties taking into account twist and misalignment of the yarns. The aim of the study is to compare estimates from analytical and FE models with those provided by the rule of mixtures, which is often used for UD materials. The FE models are generated from micro-CT images following voxel-based modelling approach. Analytical model of Naik for a twisted yarn is extended for the yarns with a non-round, elliptical cross-section. Comparison of the analytical models showed that the elliptic shape of the cross-section leads to the difference of 3.0...6.4% compared to the model with round cross-section for the twist values of 150...270 turns/m. Comparison of the analytical models with the rule of mixtures (ROM) showed that ROM overestimates the modulus for ~12...29% depending on the twist value. FE models showed overestimation of the effective properties by ROM for 13.1% on average for the five samples.

1. INTRODUCTION

Identification of the mechanical properties of flax fibres has been receiving attention due to their use as reinforcement in composite materials. Elementary flax fibre has the diameter of 15-35 μm and consists of structurally heterogeneous cell wall with an open channel in the centre called lumen [1]. The component that provides stiffness to the flax fibre is the crystalline cellulose fibrils, which are wound spirally inside the fibre. Flax fibre exhibits nonlinear mechanical properties and significant spread in the properties of individual fibres [2]. The methods, most commonly used to determine mechanical properties of the fibres are tests of individual dry technical fibres, and tests of unidirectional composite samples (impregnated fibre bundles) with back-calculation of the fibre properties [3-9]. Impregnated fibre bundle test (IFBT) is a tensile test designed to determine the Young's modulus of a fibre from the modulus of their unidirectional samples. It is standardised for glass fibres in the ASTM D2343-09 standard, but a dedicated manufacturing standard was developed by Corroller et al. [10] for flax and natural fibre-based composites in order to determine the effect of the mechanical properties, the dispersion and the fibre/matrix interface property of elementary fibres through tensile testing of unidirectional composites. According to the test procedure, a set of unidirectional fibre bundles are manufactured and tested in tension along the fibres direction. After calculation of the mean modulus of the unidirectional material, the fibre modulus is calculated using the rule of mixtures:

$$E_f = \frac{E_{UD} - E_m(1 - V_f)}{V_f}$$

where E_m is the modulus of the matrix, V_f is the fibre volume fraction and E_{UD} is the unidirectional sample modulus, determined from the experiment as seen in Corroller et al. [11]. IFBT test, in comparison to the single fibre test, tends to yield more accurate results. In the single fibre test in a dry state, a technical fibre is usually tested, which is composed of 5-20 elementary fibres with low strength pectin binding between them. This binding breaks first, which leads to the elementary fibres sliding against each other. As a consequence, the fibre modulus is significantly underestimated. In IFBT test, elementary fibres are embedded in the resin, which provides better stress transfer to the fibre and limits the sliding [12]. The fibre modulus is usually calculated from the experimental data using the rule of mixtures, which assumes

that the fibres are perfectly aligned with the longitudinal axis of the sample. However, even in glass or carbon fibre rovings certain misalignment of fibres may exist [13-16]. The twist of the yarns adds to the overall misalignment, which leads to underestimation of the fibre modulus, calculated with the rule of mixtures. The factor of twist is much more important for natural fibres, including flax, than for glass or carbon fibres, as flax yarns are usually twisted with the twist angle up to 20°, with a complex twist structure.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

A batch of 10 unidirectional flax/epoxy samples with the size of 1.5×10×250 mm was manufactured using the impregnated fibre bundle technique developed by Coroller [10]. Half of the samples were manufactured from the warp yarn, and another half from the weft. According to the specification of the manufacturer, the twist of the yarns is 210 turns/metre. Epikote 828LVEL ($\eta \approx 10-12$ Pa.s) epoxy combined with a Dytek DCH-99 hardener (15.2 phr) was used as a matrix. All samples have an average fibre volume fraction of 35% (33% in warp and 37% in weft). Five samples from the batch, two of the warp and three of the weft type were used in the study. The samples were imaged with SkyScan X-ray computed tomography system. The resolution, required for the image processing algorithms to extract fibre orientations and create a model of the material, was estimated as from 4 to 6 μm . With the resolution of 5 μm , the scanner's field of view can fit an object of maximum 11 mm in vertical direction. As the samples have the width of 1.5 mm, the scanning process could be accelerated by scanning together up to 8 sample parts, bundled to have the total width of 12 mm. Therefore, in order to minimize the occupancy of the micro-CT equipment, each sample was cut into 8 parts (Figure 1), which were stacked and fixed with layers of double-sided adhesive tape between them. The stacks were oriented so that the primary direction of the UD material was approximately aligned with the rotation axis. The samples were scanned with the tube voltage of 60 kV and the frame averaging 5 to reduce the noise. Resolution of the obtained micro-CT images was 4.44 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$.

Figure 1. Sample cutting scheme and the photo of a sample part.

Figure 2. Micro-CT image of a stack of the UD flax/epoxy sample parts.

2.1. Measurements of the yarns cross-sections

The area and the aspect ratio of the yarn cross-sections were measured in micro-CT images with ImageJ software. The cross-sections were outlined by manually fitting an ellipse to a cross-section. The measurements, 29 in total, yielded the value of $0.0707 \pm 0.0166 \text{ mm}^2$ for the cross-section area, and 2.03 ± 0.10 for the aspect ratio, where ‘ \pm ’ denotes one standard deviation. The obtained value for aspect ratio shows that the yarn cross-sections have a non-round, elliptical shape.

3. ANALYTICAL MODEL OF A TWISTED YARN

The original model of Naik [17] describes a twisted yarn with a round cross-section. The model assumes that the fibres follow a helical path along the yarn’s length, and that the twist angle decreases from the perimeter of the yarn to its centre. Here we extend this model to take into account the non-round, elliptical shape of the yarn’s cross-section. The twist angle in this case depends not only on the distance to the yarn’s centre, but also on the angular position at the perimeter. The trajectory of a fibre in this model is a helix on the surface of an elliptic cylinder (Figure 3). We assume that the fibres that are located at different distances from the centre follow elliptic helices with the same aspect ratio as of the cross-section. Parametric equation of a helix on the surface of an elliptic cylinder is:

$$x(t) = a \cos(t)$$

$$y(t) = b \sin(t)$$

$$z(t) = kt$$

Figure 3. Model of the twisted yarn with an elliptic cross-section.

where a , b are axes of the ellipse in cross-section, and k can be found from the turns per unit length parameter T of the yarn:

$$k = \frac{1}{2\pi T}$$

Equation for the tangent vector to the helix is:

$$\tau_x(t) = -a \sin(t)$$

$$\tau_y(t) = b \cos(t)$$

$$\tau_z(t) = k$$

The twist angle θ can be calculated at any position t as:

$$\cos(\theta) = \frac{\tau_z}{|\tau|} = \frac{k}{\sqrt{(a \sin t)^2 + (b \cos t)^2 + k^2}}$$

In order to integrate twist angle over an ellipse, its expression in parametric form must be converted into an explicit function of polar coordinates (φ, r) . However, this is difficult, so we approximate the twist angle in polar coordinates with the following function:

$$\tilde{\theta}(\varphi, r) = \theta_\varphi(\varphi)\theta_r(r)$$

where $\theta_r(r)$ is a linear function that changes from 0 at the centre of the ellipse to 1 at its perimeter, and $\theta_\varphi(\varphi)$ is a polynomial of 6th order, which approximates the dependence of the twist angle from the azimuthal coordinate:

Figure 4. Twist angle (in degrees) as a function of the azimuthal coordinate in the yarn's cross-section: calculated values (*) and the approximation with the 6th order polynomial (red) for the aspect ratio 2.

$$\theta_{\varphi}(\varphi) = \sum_{k=0}^6 p_k \varphi^k$$

The approximation is done by calculating the values of the twist angle and φ for a range of values of t and fitting the obtained points with the polynomial (Figure 4). The φ angle can be found as:

$$\tan(\varphi) = \frac{b \sin t}{a \cos t}$$

The effective stiffness of the twisted impregnated yarn is then found by integration over a quarter of the ellipse:

$$C_{\text{eff}} = \int_0^{\pi/2} \int_0^{r(\varphi)} C[\tilde{\theta}(\varphi, r)] r \, dr \, d\varphi$$

where

$$r(\varphi) = \frac{ab}{\sqrt{(b \cos \varphi)^2 + (a \sin \varphi)^2}}$$

and $C[\theta]$ is the stiffness matrix of the UD material, rotated by the angle θ .

4. MICRO-CT BASED FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

An alternative way to estimate the effective properties of UD flax/epoxy material is through the finite element modelling on the basis of micro-CT data. The obtained 3D images of the samples were processed with the in-house software VoxTex, which segments the image into matrix, yarns and void domains and calculates the vector field of the fibre orientations inside the yarns [18]. The output of the software is the Abaqus FE voxel model (.inp file), which represents the internal structure of the material with the matrix, yarns and voids as separate materials. Material orientations in the elements of the anisotropic material (impregnated yarn) are defined based on the fibre orientations in the sample at an element location. The model accurately represents the material's inner structure and is capable to capture twist of the yarns (Figure 5). Mechanical properties of a unidirectional composite, locally representing the impregnated yarn in the coordinate system aligned with the local fibre direction were calculated using Chamis micromechanical model [19]. The intra-yarn fibre volume fraction $V_{f,yarn}$ was calculated from the total fibre volume fraction in the sample V_f and the volume fraction of yarns (taken as solid volumes) in the model V_{yarn} as follows:

$$V_{f,yarn} = \frac{V_f}{V_{yarn}}$$

Volume fraction of yarns is calculated as a fraction of the elements of yarns in a FE model. Properties of the epoxy matrix used were as follows: Young's modulus 2.7 GPa, Poisson's coefficient 0.23. For the material of the voids, a Young's modulus of 0.01 GPa was set. The boundary conditions were chosen to simulate a tensile test: the displacements were prescribed at the top and the bottom faces of the model, and the side faces were left free. The homogenisation process involved averaging of the stress and strain fields (at element centroids) and calculation of the effective Young's modulus:

$$E_1 = \frac{\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle}{\langle \varepsilon_{11} \rangle}$$

In contrast to the general homogenization of a unit cell, where the solutions of six boundary value problems are required, an explicit modelling of a tensile test requires the solution of a single boundary value problem. The boundary displacements were applied such that to produce an average longitudinal strain $\varepsilon_z^* = 1\%$. After the calculation of the effective stiffness of the sample parts, the total effective stiffness of a sample was calculated by the model of joined elastic segments:

$$E_{sample} = \frac{N}{\sum \frac{1}{E_i}}$$

where E_i is the effective stiffness of i-th segment and N is the total number of segments.

Figure 5. Material orientations in the FE model of the UD flax/epoxy sample. The twist of the yarns is captured by the orientation field, derived from the micro-CT image.

Figure 6. Longitudinal stresses in the FE model of the UD flax/epoxy sample part.

5. RESULTS

5.1. Comparison of the analytical models

The comparison of the original model of Naik with the extended model for an elliptic yarn is presented in Table 1. The effective Young's modulus of the twisted yarn was calculated for three different values of twist, specified in turns per metre. The nominal twist value according to the specification is 210 turns/m, however it might have changed during the manufacturing of the samples. The calculations assumed the aspect ratio of the cross-section 2, the value of the fibre modulus 58 GPa and the fibre packing ratio 0.676. The fibre packing ratio was estimated on the basis of the average yarns volume fraction, which was calculated from micro-CT images, and the total fibre volume fraction in the material, which was known from the experiment. The results show that the difference between the two models increases with increasing twist value. The model for elliptic cross-section yields higher values of the effective modulus compared to the model for a round cross-section. Comparison of the two models with the estimates on the basis of the rule of mixtures showed that ROM tends to overestimate the modulus, with a higher overestimation for higher values of twist.

Table 1. Model predictions for the impregnated yarn modulus, and the comparison with the ROM estimates.

Turns Per Metre	Model prediction, GPa		Difference, %	ROM prediction, GPa	Model/ROM	
	Elliptic cross-section	Round cross-section			Elliptic/ROM	Round/ROM
150	35.2	34.1	3.0%	40.1	87.8%	85.2%
210	31.8	30.3	4.8%	40.1	79.4%	75.7%
270	28.6	26.8	6.4%	40.1	71.3%	66.9%

5.2. Finite element models

The values for the UD material effective modulus, estimated from FE models, are given in Table 2. Note that these values are related to the UD material, whereas the effective properties reported in the previous section are related to the impregnated yarn. However, our goal here is to compare these two methods with the rule of mixtures. The values are given for the five samples, which were modelled. The results show that the ratios of the estimates with FEM to the estimates with ROM are close to each other for different samples. The variation of the absolute values of the moduli is therefore caused mainly by the variation in the fibre volume fraction (Figure 7). The average FEM/ROM ratio for the five samples is 86.9%. The contribution of the twist and misalignment to the reduction of the modulus is therefore 13.1% on average.

Table 2. Estimates of the UD material modulus from FE models and the rule of mixtures.

Sample	Vf	FEM, Ef=58	ROM	FEM/ROM ratio for UD modulus	(ROM-FEM)/ROM
WARP 3	0.33	18.36	20.95	87.6%	12.4%
WARP 2	0.31	17.14	19.84	86.4%	13.6%
WEFT 4	0.39	21.20	24.27	87.3%	12.7%
WEFT 3	0.38	20.88	23.71	88.0%	12.0%
WEFT 2	0.36	19.26	22.61	85.2%	14.8%

Figure 7. The UD modulus, calculated from the FE models, as a function of the fibre volume fraction.

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The results of FE calculations showed that the degree of twist and misalignment, which lead to the reduction of the UD material modulus, are close in the five samples that were modelled. The variation of the UD modulus is caused mainly by the variation in fibre volume fraction. The average value of ROM/FEM predictions ratio can therefore be used to introduce a correction to ROM without need to perform expensive simulations for each sample in a batch. Such a correction is useful in case of IFBT tests aimed at determining the fibre modulus, otherwise the derived fibre modulus will be underestimated. The results of the analytical models showed that the value of twist that produces the reduction of stiffness close to the one predicted with FEM is 150 turns/m, which is lower than the nominal 210 turns/m from specification. It may indicate that the yarns were partially untwisted during the manufacturing of the UD samples. However, at the moment there is no way to measure the value of twist directly from CT data. The comparison of the original model of Naik with the extended model for the yarn with an elliptic cross-section showed that the difference between these two model increases with increasing twist and reaches 6.4% at the twist of 270 turns/m. Further work shall be focused at the development of the methods to characterize the fibre geometry and calculate the degree of twist from high-resolution micro-CT images.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement no ACP2-GA-2012-314562-QUICOM (development of micro-CT and FEA based processing); and from the fund "Fonds de recherche du Québec - Nature et technologies" FQRNT (IFBT testing and material characterisation). The X-ray computed tomography images have been made on the X-ray computed tomography facilities at the KU Leuven, financed by the Hercules Foundation (project AKUL 09/001: Micro- and nano-CT for the hierarchical analysis of materials).

REFERENCES

- [1] Kersani M, Lomov SV, Van Vuure AW, Bouabdallah A, Verpoest I. Damage in flax/epoxy quasi-unidirectional woven laminates under quasi-static tension. *Journal of Composite Materials*. 2015;49(4):403-413.
- [2] Baley C. Analysis of the flax fibres tensile behaviour and analysis of the tensile stiffness increase. *Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing*. 2002;33(7):939-948.
- [3] Baley C, Le Duigou A, Bourmaud A, Davies P. Influence of drying on the mechanical behaviour of flax fibres and their unidirectional composites. *Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing*. 2012;43(8):1226-1233.
- [4] Baley C, Perrot Y, Busnel F, Guezenoc H, Davies P. Transverse tensile behaviour of unidirectional plies reinforced with flax fibres. *Materials Letters*. 2006;60(24):2984-2987.
- [5] Charlet K, Beakou A. Mechanical characterization and modeling of interfacial lamella within a flax bundle. 11th International Conference on the Mechanical Behavior of Materials (Icm11). 2011;10.
- [6] Charlet K, Eve S, Jernot JP, Gomina M, Breard J. Tensile deformation of a flax fiber. *Mesomechanics* 2009. 2009;1(1):233-236.
- [7] Modniks J, Joffe R, Andersons J. Model of the mechanical response of short flax fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites. 11th International Conference on the Mechanical Behavior of Materials (Icm11). 2011;10.
- [8] Sparnins E, Modniks J, Andersons J. Experimental Study of the Mechanical Properties of Unidirectional Flax Fiber Composite. *Icm15: 15th International Conference on Experimental Mechanics*. 2012.
- [9] Sparnins E, Nystrom B, Andersons J. Interfacial shear strength of flax fibers in thermoset resins evaluated via tensile tests of UD composites. *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*. 2012;36:39-43.
- [10] Coroller G, Lefeuvre A, Le Duigou A, Bourmaud A, Ausias G, Gaudry T, et al. Effect of flax fibres individualisation on tensile failure of flax/epoxy unidirectional composite. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. 2013;51(0):62-70.
- [11] Coroller G, Lefeuvre A, Le Duigou A, Bourmaud A, Ausias G, Gaudry T, et al. Effect of flax fibres individualisation on tensile failure of flax/epoxy unidirectional composite. *Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing*. 2013;51:62-70.
- [12] Hendrickx K. Investigation of the improvement in mechanical properties of flax fibre bio-composites using a novel polymerization condensation reaction. 2014.
- [13] Barwick SC, Papathanasiou TD. Identification of fiber misalignment in continuous fiber composites. *Polymer Composites*. 2003;24(3):475-486.
- [14] Kratmann KK, Sutcliffe MPF, Lilleheden LT, Pyrz R, Thomsen OT. A novel image analysis procedure for measuring fibre misalignment in unidirectional fibre composites. *Composites Science and Technology*. 2009;69(2):228-238.
- [15] Pinho ST, Iannucci L, Robinson P. Physically based failure models and criteria for laminated fibre-reinforced composites with emphasis on fibre kinking. Part II: FE implementation. *Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing*. 2006;37(5):766-777.
- [16] Pinho ST, Iannucci L, Robinson P. Physically-based failure models and criteria for laminated fibre-reinforced composites with emphasis on fibre kinking: Part I: Development. *Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing*. 2006;37(1):63-73.
- [17] Naik NK, Madhavan V. Twisted impregnated yarns: elastic properties. *Journal of Strain Analysis for Engineering Design*. 2000;35(2):83-91.
- [18] Straumit I, Lomov SV, Wevers M. Quantification of the internal structure and automatic generation of voxel models of textile composites from X-ray computed tomography data. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. 2015;69(0):150-158.
- [19] Chamis CC. Simplified Composite Micromechanics Equations for Hygral, Thermal, and Mechanical-Properties. *Sampe Quarterly-Society for the Advancement of Material and Process Engineering*.

1984;15(3):14-23.